

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

18 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 18, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 18, ISSUE 1

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович

*PhD, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena

*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхис кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор. Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

*Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
2-сон Даволаш факултети декани,
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент.
Самарқанд, Ўзбекистон.*

Миржурев Элбек Миршавкатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
УзССВ Тиббий ходимларни касбий малакасини
ривожлантириши марказининг Нейрореабилитация
кафедраси мудири, Тошкент, Ўзбекистон*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

PhD, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Мирджурев Эльбек Миршавкатович

Заведующий кафедрой Нейрореабилитации Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников МЗ РУз, д.м.н., профессор Ташкент, Узбекистан

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD, Docent Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich

*Dean of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2, Samarkand State
Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate
Professor. Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Mirjuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich

*Head of the Department of Neurorehabilitation Center
for the development of professional qualification of
medical workers, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2111-4388>*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

ANESTHESIOLOGY, RESUSCITATION, INTENSIVE CARE

1. **Matlubov Mansur Muratovich, Muminov Abdukhalim Abduvakilovich**
ASSESSMENT OF THE DEGREE OF PRESERVATION OF CORONARY RESERVES IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH MITRAL STENOSIS.....11
2. **Khudoyberdieva Gulrukh Sobirovna, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich, Kasparova Gayane Arturovna**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE CONDITION OF WOMEN DURING CESAREAN SECTION UNDER SPINAL ANESTHESIA AND MEDICAL SEDATION.....16
3. **Khudoyberdieva Gulrukh Sobirovna, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich**
SEDATION AND PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL STATUS OF WOMEN IN REGIONAL ANESTHESIA FOR CAESAREAN SECTION. CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM.....24
4. **Sharipov Isroil Latipovich**
HEMODYNAMIC GRADATIONS DURING COMBINED USAGE OF EXTRACORPORAL DETOXIFICATION METHODS IN CHILDREN WITH RENAL FAILURE.....31
5. **Pardaev Shukur Kuylievich, Sharipov Isroil Latipovich**
APPLICATION OF CENTRAL NEURAXIAL ANESTHESIA IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LUMBAR-SACRAL DISC HERNIATIONS.....38
6. **Yusupov Jasur Tolibovich, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich**
ENHANCING INTENSIVE CARE FOR PATIENTS FOLLOWING CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING (LITERATURE REVIEW).....44

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

7. **Ahmedova Aziza Tayirovna, Rasulova Feruza Golibovna**
ASSESSMENT OF PERINATAL COMPLICATIONS RISK USING REMOTE CARDIOTOCOGRAPHY MONITORING.....52
8. **Agababyan Larisa Rubenovna, Usmankulova Habiba Mizrobjonovna**
NEW TREATMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME.....59
9. **Nasirova Zebiniso Azizovna**
APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ANEMIA IN HEAVY MENSTRUAL BLEEDING.....66
10. **Zakirova Nodira Islomovna, Yuldasheva Farangiz Ismatilloevna**
CORRECTION AND TACTICS OF PREGNANCY ADMINISTRATION IN CASE OF VIOLATIONS OF THE VAGINAL ECOSYSTEM.....76

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

11. **Orzikulov Azam Orzikulovich, Haydarov Akbar Haydarovich**
ANTIVIRAL THERAPY IN VIRAL HEPATITIS “C” DISEASE EFFICIENCY (A CASE FROM PRACTICE).....80
12. **Oslanov Absamat Abdurakhimovich, Soibnazarov Orzukul Ernazarovich**
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE VIRAL LOAD TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIVER FIBROSIS IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS «B» (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAMARKAND REGION).....86
13. **Kadirov Zhonibek Fayzullayevich, Rizaev Jasur Alimdjanovich, Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdiyevich**
MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL ACTIVATION IN HIV INFECTION.....92

ENDOCRINOLOGY

14. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Rasulov Jamshedjon Shavkatovich**
EFFICACY OF FOLK REMEDIES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS AT RISK OF STROKE.....106
15. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Ergashev Asadullo Ubaydullo o'g'li**
THE IMPORTANCE OF BLOOD RHEOLOGY IN DIABETES IN THE ORIGIN OF ISCHEMIC STROKE AND THE EFFECT OF HIRUDOTHERAPY ON BLOOD RHEOLOGY.....111
16. **Fozilova Umida Kamalovna, Khabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
THE ROLE OF GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN PREVENTING DENTAL COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES(REVIEW ARTICLE).....116
17. **Saidova Shakhnoza Aripovna, Yakubov Abdusalol Vahobovich, Pulatova Durдона Baxadirovna**
THE EFFECT OF GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONISM ON DIVERSE ASPECTS OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES AND OBESITY.....122

MORPHOLOGY

18. **Boboev Askar Ibodullaevich, Oripov Firdavs Suratovich, Boboev Ibodullo Boboevich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE GALLBLADDER WALL IN EXPERIMENTAL CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS.....128
19. **M.A. Abdullayeva, O.O. Zaripova.**
DETERMINATION OF THE ACCUMULATION LEVEL OF ARTIFICIAL FOOD COLORANTS E 171 AND E 173 IN THE BRAIN.....135
20. **Mamataliyev Abdumalik Rasulovich**
ANATOMICAL AND TOPOGRAPHICAL STRUCTURE OF THE EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCT IN EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS.....140
21. **Ismailov Jasur Mardonovich**
ABOUT BRONCHIECTASIS AS A TYPE OF CHRONIC NONSPECIFIC LUNG DISEASE.....144
22. **Ismailov Jasur Mardonovich, Norjigitov Azamat Musokulovich**
MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF BRONCHI AND LUNG TISSUES IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIECTASIS.....150
23. **Juraev Kamoliddin Danabaevich, Islamov Shavkat Erjigitovich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYMUS IN NEWBORNS IN THE LATE NEONATAL PERIOD.....158
24. **Rakhimova Gulnoz Shamsievna, Teshayev Shuxrat Jumayevich.**
ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE TESTES ON THE FIRST DAY AFTER ACUTE TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY.....168

NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY

25. **Ruzmetova Saodat Umarjonovna**
FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EARLY POSTNATAL HEALTH IN CHILDREN WHO HAVE SUFFERED PERINATAL CNS DAMAGE.....173
26. **Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadullaevna, Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Abruev Khudoerkhon Oybekovich**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE IN THYROID HOMEOSTASIS DISRUPTION.....178

27. **Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Kilichev Ibodullo Abdullayevich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Khudoyberganov Nurmamat Yusupovich, Pazilova Aida Sultanovna**
CORRECTION OF COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENTS IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA IN OUTPATIENT SETTINGS.....185
28. **Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadulloevna, Nurboeva Iroda Samariddin Qizi**
PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....192
29. **Khamdamova Bakhora Komiljonovna, Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich, Muhammadiyeva Dilafruz Po'lot qizi**
INNOVATIVE METHODS OF THERAPY FOR NEUROVASCULAR DISORDERS IN LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHIES.....202
30. **Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadulloevna**
DANCE MOVEMENT REHABILITATION TO REDUCE COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH EARLY-ONSET PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....209
31. **Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich, Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadulloevna, Zoxidjonova Shahnoza Zoxidjonovna**
FEATURES OF PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL AND AUTONOMIC DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PAIN SYNDROME WITH RADICULOPATHIES.....216
32. **Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna.**
IMPROVING MEASURES FOR REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES DUE TO NERVOUS SYSTEM DISEASES.....222
33. **Raimova Malika Mukhamedjanovna, Yodgarova Umida Gaybulloyevna**
IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS BY STUDYING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESTLESS LEGS SYNDROME AND HYPOTHYROIDISM.....229

UROLOGY

34. **Allazov Iskandar Salax Ugli, Allazov Salax Allazovich, Ablyatifov Aziz Baxtiyarovich**
OUTPATIENT UROLOGICAL-POLICLINICAL CARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....235
35. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich, Allazov Iskandar Salakh Ogli, Ergashev Arslonbek Shuxratjon Ogli**
MEDICAL-SOCIAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES. LITERATURE REVIEW.....242
36. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich, Batirov Bekhzod Amindjanovich.**
DISTRIBUTION OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES AND METHODS FOR THEIR DETECTION PHARMACOLOGY AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINE.....247
37. **Mirrakhimova Maktuba Habibullaevna, Nishanbaeva Nilufar Yunusjanovna**
FILAGGRIN DEFECT IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS AND MODERN METHODS OF CORRECTION.....256
38. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Rasulov Jamshedjon Shavkatovich.**
HIRUDOTHERAPY, THE EFFECT OF VARIOUS TREATMENT METHODS.....262

PEDIATRICS AND PEDIATRIC SURGERY

39. **Abdullaev Zafar Bobirovich, Agzamkhodjaev Saidanvar Talatovich**
ANTENATAL DIAGNOSTICS OF BLADDER EXTROPHY: CONTEMPORARY POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS.....267
40. **Rakhimova Durdona Zhurakulovna**
HYGIENIC ASSESSMENT OF ACTUAL NUTRITION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN.....274

41. **Ganiev Abdurashid Ganievich, Sanakulov Abdulatif Burkhanovich**
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE FAMILY OF A SICK CHILD.....284
42. **Naimushina Elena Serafimovna, Kilina Alla Vladimirovna, Chervinskih Tatyana Anatolyevna**
GENDER-SPECIFIC CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF OBESITY IN ADOLESCENTS.....293
43. **Nuritdinova Gavhar Taipovna, Inakova Barno Bahodirovna, Abduvahobova Gulmira, Arzibekova Umida Abdukodirovna.**
DELAYED NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN NEWBORNS WITH MODERATE AND SEVERE ASPHYXIA.....299
44. **Ollabergenov Odilbek, Baratov Feruz**
MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN ACUTE PLEURAL EMPYEMA IN CHILDREN.....305

ONCOLOGY

45. **Ulmasov Firdavs Gayratovich, Esankulova Bustonoy Sobirovna.**
THE ROLE OF VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR (VEGF) IN OVARIAN CANCER WITH PERITONEAL CARCINOMATOSIS IN STAGES III AND IV.....311
46. **Kahharov Alisher, Khodjayeva Nozima**
THE IMPACT OF FERTILITY PRESERVATION PROGRAMS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF WOMEN WITH ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES.....318
47. **Zaripova Parvina Ilkhomovna, Yorov Lutfillo Shukurulloevich, Kutlumurotov Otabek Bekjanovich, Juraev Mirjalol Dehkonovich**
ABOUT THE PROBLEM OF BREAST CANCER RECURRENCE CAUSES.....323

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

48. **Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Gaibullaev Elbek Azizbekovich, Akramova Nozima Akramovna, Pustovetova Maria Genadievna**
ANALYSIS OF CYTOKINE PROFILE IN GINGIVAL CREVICULAR FLUID OF PATIENTS WITH AGGRESSIVE PERIODONTITIS: PATHOGENETIC AND DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS.....333
49. **Daminova Nargiza Ravshanovna, Makhkamova Oqila Abdushukurovna, Sadikova Dilfuza Ravshanbekovna, Inogamov Sherzod Muhamatisakovich**
EVALUATION OF THE IMMUNOLOGICAL AND RESPIRATORY STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA WITH COMORBID PATHOLOGY OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....338
50. **Axmedov Xurshid Kamalovich**
ASSESSMENT OF STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN PERIODONTAL TISSUES DURING PROSTHETICS WITH METAL-CERAMIC AND ZIRCONIUM DENTURES.....344
51. **Olimova Dildora Vohid qizi**
DENTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH END-STAGE CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE (A STUDY OF PATIENTS RECEIVING AND NOT RECEIVING HEMODIALYSIS).352
52. **Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich, Mardonova Dildora Kasimovna**
IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR HYPERTROPHIC GINGIVITIS IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY.....358

53. **Khotamova Madina Anvarovna, Odiljonova Mukhimaoy Savlatovna**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF PERIODONTITIS AND THE ORGANIZATION OF DENTAL MEASURES FOR WORKERS OF METAL PROCESSING ENTERPRISES.....366
54. **Umarova Makhfuza Usmanovna**
THE IMPACT OF CHRONIC USE OF NICOTINE-CONTAINING PRODUCTS ON THE PROGRESSION OF INFLAMMATORY-DYSTROPHIC DISEASES OF THE ORAL CAVITY: CLINICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS.....370
55. **Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich, Allazarov Kuvondik Azadovich**
IMPROVING THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENITIS.....377
56. **Allazarov Kuvondik Azadovich, Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich.**
USE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF OZONE IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENITIS385
57. **Mardonova Dildora Kasimovna, Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS FOR EXAMINING PERIODONT TISSUE DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY393
58. **Akhmedov Ilhom Ibrohimovich, Kamalova Feruza Raxmatullaeva.**
CHANGES IN MICROFLORA NON-SPECIFIC FACTORS PROTECTION OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN CHILDREN WITH INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF MAXILLOFACIAL.....401
59. **Yuldashev Forrukh Farkhod Ugli, Kuryazov Akbar Kuranboevich, Khabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES AND APPROACHES TO THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF DENTAL DISEASES IN DEAF-MUTE CHILDREN (REVIEW ARTICLE).....406
60. **Navruzova Ugilxon Orzijon Qizi, Xabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
THE ROLE OF IMMUNE STATUS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS.....414
61. **Tojiyev Feruz Ibodulla ugli, Beysenbayev Nurbek Kunanbay ugli, Ismoilkhojaeva Komila G'ani qizi.**
RECONSTRUCTION OF MANDIBULAR DEFECTS IN CHILDREN WITH INDIVIDUALLY MANUFACTURED TITANIUM IMPLANTS AFTER REMOVAL OF BENIGN TUMORS.....419

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

62. **Giyasov Zaynitdin Asamutdinovich, Gulyamov Dilshod Erkinovich**
FORENSIC ASSESSMENT OF INJURIES TO MAJOR JOINTS IN ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS.....425

THERAPY AND INTERNAL MEDICINE

63. **Tashkenbayeva Eleonora Negmatovna, Esankulov Mukhammad Olimovich**
SIGNIFICANCE OF UROMODULIN IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....431

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

64. **Abrolov Hakimjon Kobiljonovich, Xolmurotov Akmal Abdumalikovich, Irisov Ortikali Tulaevich, Berdiev Kobiljon Bahromovich, Rakhimberganov Khusanboy Davlatnazarovich**
NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ASCENDING AORTIC ANEURYSM.....437

65. **Ashirov Mavlon Umirzakovitch.**
BIOMECHANICAL INSIGHTS INTO MDICO FOR FLATFOOT CORRECTION.....445
66. **Khodjanov Iskandar Yunusovich, Ubaydullaev Sherozbek Farkhodovich**
IMPROVING THE METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF VALGOUS DEFORMATION OF THE ELBOW JOINT.....459
67. **Mamasoliev Bakhodir Mamausupovich**
FEATURES OF THROMBOEMBOLIC COMPLICATIONS PREVENTION DURING SURGICAL TREATMENT OF KNEE JOINT DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LOWER LIMB VENOUS DISEASE.....468
68. **Melibayev Salimjon Tashtanovich, Karshiboyev Abduvakhob Jambojevich, Nomazov Olim Ergash Og'Li, Jurayev Ilhom G'ulomovich**
VERTEBRAL COMPRESSION FRACTURES: CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS, AND MODERN TREATMENT STRATEGIES.....475
69. **Karshiboyev Abduvakhob Jambojevich, Melibayev Salimjon Tashtanovich, Nomazov Olim Ergash Og'Li, Jalilov Khusan Mukhitdinovich.**
HIP FRACTURE, DIAGNOSIS, SURGICAL TREATMENT, REHABILITATION, THROMBOEMBOLIC PROPHYLAXIS, BISPHTHONATES, FALL PREVENTION.....489
70. **Kholkhudjayev Farrukh Ikramovich**
RESULTS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ROTATOR CUFF INJURIES OF THE SHOULDER JOINT.....502
71. **Tilyakov Xasan Azizovich, Temurov Alisher Akmaljon O'g'li, Xursanov Muxriddin Xusniddin O'g'li, Yusupov Sohijon Saitxon O'g'li, Tolmasov Mirjalol Mirzohid O'g'li.**
RESULTS OF THE APPLICATION OF ADVANCED OSTEOSYNTHESIS IN DIAPHYSEAL FRACTURES OF THE HUMERUS.....508

RADIATION IMAGING

72. **Ikramova Zulfiya Tulkinovna, Rozikhodjaeva Gulnora Ahmedovna, Soipova Guzal Gulomidinovna**
ASSESSMENT OF TOTAL CEREBRAL BLOOD FLOW IN PATIENTS WITH CAROTIC ATHEROSCLEROSIS.....515

SURGERY

73. **Akhmedov Adkham Ibadullaevich, Fayazov Abdulaziz Djalilovich**
PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF MOTOR-EVACUATION DYSFUNCTION OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS.....523
74. **Sayinaev Farrukh Karamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich**
LAPAROSCOPIC AND OPEN HERNIOPLASTY FOR VENTRAL HERNIAS: SURGICAL OUTCOMES AND COMPLICATIONS ASSESSMENT.....532
75. **Daminov Feruz Asatullaevich, Shomurodov Khabibullo Abdumalik Ugli, Rakhmonov Kosim Erdanovich.**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TACTICS IN ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE CHOLECYSTITIS: THE ROLE OF LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY AND RISK FACTOR ANALYSIS.....539
76. **Khayitov Laziz Milionerovich, Khakimov Erkin Abdikhalilovich, Zuvaytov Shoxrux G'ayrat o'g'li, Abrorov Shahbozjon Nematzoda**
THE ROLE ENDOBRONCHIAL COMPLEX THERAPY AT PATIENTS WITH THE INHALATION TRAUMA.....544

OPHTHALMOLOGY

77. **Fayzieva Dilorom Buritoshevna, Akhmedova Dilafruz Baxadirovna, Mirzaev Dilshodbek Akhmedovich.**
VISUAL DISORDERS AND THEIR IMPACT ON PERIPHERAL VISION AND EYE MOVEMENT COORDINATION.....549

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

УДК:616-001/09.616-072/085

AKHMEDOV Adkham Ibadullaevich

PhD

Samarkand State Medical University

FAYAZOV Abdulaziz Djalilovich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor

Republican Research Center of Emergency Medicine

EARLY SURGICAL TREATMENT OF DEEP BURNS IN ELDERLY PATIENTS

For citation: Akhmedov Adkham, Fayazov Abdulaziz. Prevention and treatment of motor-evacuation dysfunction of the gastrointestinal tract in severely burned patients // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2025, vol. 10, issue 1, pp.523-531

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15008496>

ANNOTATION

The article is dedicated to the results of surgical treatment of elderly and senile patients with deep burns. The available data indicates that the best results can be achieved with a single-stage autologous skin grafting to close all wounds in one step for limited deep burns. For extensive burns, the best results are achieved using delayed autologous skin grafting performed in 1-2 stages. It has been reported that the use of early surgical intervention methods for deep burns in elderly and senile patients significantly reduces the recovery time of skin integrity, the frequency of burn disease complications, and mortality.

Keywords: deep burns, autologous skin grafting, surgical necrectomy, autologous skin transplant

АХМЕДОВ Адхам Ибадуллаевич

PhD

Самарканд Давлат тиббиёт университети

ФАЯЗОВ Абдулазиз Джалилович

Тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор

Республика шошилинич тиббий ёрдам илмий маркази

КЕКСА ВА ҚАРИ ЁШИДАГИ БЕМОРЛАРДА ЧУҚУР КУЙИШЛАРНИ ЭРТА ХИРУРГИК ДАВОЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола чуқур куйиш жарохати олган кекса ва қари беморларни хирургик даволаш натижаларига бағишланган. Кекса ва қари беморларни хирургик даволашда чегараланган чуқур куйиш жараохатларида бир босқичда барча яраларни ёпиш учун бир босқичли аутодермопластикадан ҳамда кенг кўламли куйишлар учун эса, кечиктирилган аутодермопластика фойдаланиш энг яхши натижаларга эришиш мумкинлиги тўғрисида

маълумотлар келтирилган. Кекса ва қари беморларда эрта жарроҳлик усулларини қўллаш терининг тикланиш вақтини, куйиш касаллиги асоратлари ва ўлимнинг частотасини сезиларли даражада камайтириши мумкинлиги баён қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: чуқур куйиш, аутодермопластика, хирургик некрэктомия, аутодермотрансплантат

АХМЕДОВ Адхам Ибадуллаевич

PhD

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

ФАЯЗОВ Абдулазиз Джалилович

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор

Республиканский научный центр экстренной медицинской помощи

РАННЕЕ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ГЛУБОКИХ ОЖОГОВ У ПОЖИЛЫХ И ПРЕСТАРЕЛЫХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена результатам хирургического лечения с глубокими ожогами у пациентов пожилого и старческого возраста. При хирургическом лечении у пациентов пожилого и старческого возраста имеются данные о том, что наилучшие результаты одномоментной аутодермопластики с закрытием всех ран за один этап при ограниченных глубоких ожогах, а при обширных ожогах лучшие результаты - использование отсроченной аутодермопластики, выполненной за 1-2 этапа. Сообщалось, что применение раннее методов хирургического вмешательства с глубокими ожогами, у пациентов пожилого и старческого возраста, позволяет существенно уменьшить сроки восстановления кожных покровов, частоту осложнений ожоговой болезни и летальность.

Ключевые слова: глубоких ожогов, аутодермопластика, хирургические некрэктомии, аутодермотрансплантат

One of the main demographic trends in the world is population aging, with a continuous increase in the number of people aged 60 and older, including within the age group over 80. It is known that elderly and senile individuals, like children, are a high-risk group for thermal injury [1,7,11].

The severity of injuries in elderly and senile patients is determined not only by the area and depth of burn wounds but also by comorbidities and age-related degeneration of all organs and systems [5,8,10]. Burn injuries typically exacerbate existing chronic diseases, significantly worsening the patients' condition and leading to complications, thereby deteriorating treatment outcomes [3,4,9].

In geriatric patients, the application of active surgical treatment methods is limited [2,6,12]. The main limiting factors are the high risk of surgical intervention and the presence of severe comorbid conditions.

Objective of the study. To determine the most rational surgical tactics based on the area of deep burns in elderly and senile patients.

Materials and Methods. The clinical research results from the comprehensive treatment of 69 patients in the combustiology department of the Samarkand City Medical Association from 2019 to 2023. Inclusion criteria for the study groups were: age 60 years and older; presence of deep burns of III-B to IV degree. All 69 patients had a Baux index exceeding 60 units.

Based on the clinical course and severity of thermal injury, severely burned elderly and senile patients were divided into three groups. The first group comprised 29 (42.1%) patients with a prognostic index from 61 to 80 units, indicating a relatively favorable prognosis. The second group included 27 (39.1%) patients with a Baux index (BI) from 81 to 100 units, indicating a doubtful prognosis. The third group consisted of 13 (18.8%) patients with an unfavorable prognosis (BI over 100 units). The average BI was 85.14 ± 15.97 units.

The study group included 39 (56.9%) men and 30 (43.1%) women. Among the observed cases, 48.6% of the patients sustained thermal injuries from flames. Thermal injuries from hot liquids also constituted a significant etiological share in this age group, accounting for 39.4%. Patients with contact burns (5.5%), burns from hot oil (3.7%), and electrothermal injuries (2.8%) were extremely rare.

The total burn area in patients ranged from 0.5% to 70% of the body surface, with an average of $16.7 \pm 13.1\%$ of the body surface area. All burn degrees were considered in the total area assessment - I, II, III-A, B, and IV degrees. Only 21 (30.4%) patients had limited burns of less than 10% of the body surface. In contrast, 13 (18.8%) patients had extensive burns covering more than one-third of the body surface.

The prevalence of deep burns due to different causative factors showed that in more than half of the patients with smaller areas of deep burns (up to 3% and 7% of body surface area), scalds from hot water were most common (55% and 50%, respectively). In contrast, among those with more extensive burns, flames were the primary etiological factor. In our observations, deep contact burns did not exceed 6% of body surface area, and deep electrical burns reached up to 9% of body surface area.

It is well known that one of the characteristic features of geriatric patients is the high frequency of one or more comorbidities. In this study, we considered it appropriate to account only for clinically significant diseases that could affect the outcome and treatment strategy. Overall, serious comorbidities were noted in 51 (73.9%) patients. As expected, cardiovascular diseases were the most frequent: 56% of the patients examined suffered from ischemic heart disease, and 20.2% of elderly and senile burn patients had arterial hypertension, corresponding to average figures for this age group. Circulatory disorders included cases of acute cerebrovascular accidents in the medical history (21.1%) and the consequences of chronic cerebrovascular insufficiency (1.8%). Additionally, about one in five to six burn patients had respiratory diseases (14.7%), diabetes mellitus (22.9%), and digestive diseases (20.2%). Isolated cases included chronic alcoholism (2.8%), kidney diseases (0.9%), and malignant neoplasms (0.9%).

In elderly and senile patients, we utilized surgical debridement (SD). Based on the timing, SDs were classified as early or delayed. In older age groups, early surgical debridement (ESD) was performed in the first week after the thermal injury, provided there were no inflammatory processes in the wound area. Delayed surgical debridement (DSD) was performed between 8 to 42 days after the injury.

Results and discussion. The approximately equal susceptibility of men and women in the older age group to thermal injuries may seem somewhat surprising at first glance. It is well known that almost all types of injuries, including burns, occur significantly more frequently in men. However, in our observations, there was no correlation between gender and the frequency of thermal injuries among elderly and senile patients.

The average timing for performing early surgical debridement (ESD) was 6.1 ± 0.2 days. Delayed surgical debridement (DSD) was performed, on average, at 9.7 ± 0.7 days.

Fig. 1. Distribution of patients by timing of necrectomy, n=69
Delayed surgical debridement, n=47

A total of 22 (31.9%) elderly and senile patients who underwent SD had early debridement, while 47 (68.1%) had delayed debridement. In 18 (26.1%) cases, SD was performed later than 14 days post-injury due to the following reasons:

1. The need for prolonged preoperative preparation due to the severe general condition of the patients.
2. The deepening of III-A degree burns.
3. Late hospital admission (9-40 days post-injury).

In cases of extremely severe thermal injury, with a Baux Index (BI) exceeding 100 units, general and local conditions allowed for early surgical debridement (ESD) in only 2 cases (see Fig. 2). Among those with less severe thermal injuries, with a BI of 81-100 units, ESD was performed in less than a quarter of patients (22.2%). Conversely, for elderly patients with a BI ranging from 60-80 units, we were able to utilize the benefits of so-called active surgical tactics (early debridement) in approximately half of the cases (48.3%).

Fig. 2. Correlation between the severity of thermal injury and the timing of surgical debridement.

Fig. 3. Distribution of patients based on the nature of autodermplasty and debridement, n (%)

The average area of necrotic tissue removal during necrectomy was $11.7 \pm 0.7\%$ of body surface area (BSA). This indicator did not significantly differ between the groups of patients undergoing ESD and DSD ($12.1 \pm 0.5\%$ and $10.8 \pm 1.2\%$ BSA, respectively). However, among burn patients with a Baux Index (BI) exceeding 80 units, we had to remove necrotic tissues over a significantly larger area (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Average area of necrectomy during ESD and DSD in burn patients with different severity of thermal injury, % body surface.

Groups	ESD, n=22	DSD, n=47	average, n=69
Baux index 60-80, n=29	7,3±0,6	7,1±0,7	7,2±0,5
Baux index > 81-100, n=27	13,0±0,7	12,6±2,4	12,9±1,5
Baux index > 100, n=13	15,1±0,8	14,2±2,2	14,7±1,4
Total, n=69	12,1±0,5	10,8±1,2	11,7±0,7

After performing fascial necrectomy, simultaneous autodermplasty was carried out. Simultaneous autodermplasty was performed only in a quarter - 17 (24.6%) - of elderly operated patients (see Fig. 3). Perforated skin grafts were used in all cases. Generally, favorable conditions for simultaneous autodermplasty were present in elderly patients with limited deep burns. Delayed autodermplasty was performed in 52 (75.4%) patients within 1-10 days after surgical necrectomy, on average 4.1 ± 1.9 days later.

The possibility of simultaneous radical excision of necrotic tissues and, consequently, performing simultaneous autodermplasty was not significantly dependent on the timing of debridement. Simultaneous autodermplasty was achieved in only 36.4% and 19.1% of patients undergoing ESD and DSD, respectively, within their respective groups ($\chi^2=0.122$). Typically, these were burn patients with predominantly limited deep burns (burn area of IIIb-IV degree exceeding 7% of body surface in only 2 (2.9%) patients undergoing simultaneous autodermplasty).

Delayed autodermplasty following ESD was performed in 14 (63.6%) burn patients on average 2.9 days later. In one case, autodermplasty was delayed for 32 days due to general medical reasons (severe prolonged pneumonia, sequelae of a previous stroke). Additionally, in 2 patients from the DSD group, autodermplasty was delayed by 2 weeks (17 and 22 days) after necrotic tissue excision due to the development of secondary necrosis and sluggish wound healing in the context of diabetes mellitus.

On average, the timeframe for autodermplasty after trauma in the group of patients undergoing surgical necrectomy was 13.4 ± 0.9 days (see Table 2). Depending on the type of debridement - early or delayed - the closure times with skin grafts differed approximately twofold, with respective averages of 8.4 ± 0.5 and 16.1 ± 1.2 days ($p < 0.001$). Although these figures are somewhat conditional, considering both simultaneous and delayed autodermplasty, they unequivocally highlight the advantages of early necrectomy in reducing the recovery time of skin coverage.

Table 2.

Average timings of autodermplasty after injury with primary and delayed surgical debridement

Groups	ESD, n=22	DSD, n=47	Average
Baux index 60-80, n=29	7,7±1,4	15,7±0,9	12,9±1,1
Baux index > 81-100, n=27	9,8±1,6	15,5±1,5	13,7±1,8
Baux index > 100, n=13	10,2±2,3	17,9±1,3	15,5±1,7
Total, n=69	8,4±0,5	16,1±1,2	13,4±0,9

The timing of autodermplasty (ADP) did not significantly differ among patients with varying severity of thermal injury. For instance, the difference between patients with a Baux index within 60-80 units and those with Baux index over 80 units in terms of this indicator was 1-2 days ($p > 0.05$).

Overall, among burn patients with similar severity of thermal injury, the difference in timing for wound closure using autodermotransplants can reach up to 15 days. The choice of timing for surgical debridement (SD) and subsequent ADP was determined by the patient's admission time to the hospital, their condition, presence of comorbidities and complications, among other factors. For example, in patients with Bo index over 80 units undergoing primary SD with simultaneous ADP, wounds closed with transplants in 6.3 ± 0.2 days, whereas with delayed SD and subsequent ADP, closure occurred in 17.0 ± 0.8 days (Table 3). Similar operations were conducted within these timeframes for patients with Bo index over 100 units.

Table 3.

Average timing of immediate and delayed autodermoplasty (ADP) after trauma.

Groups	ADP timing (in days)			
	ESD, n=22		DSD, n=47	
	Simultaneous ADP, n=8	Delayed ADP, n=14	Simultaneous ADP, n=9	Delayed ADP, n=38
Baux index 60-80, n=29	5,5±1,6	10,1±2,0	10,9±1,7	20,2±0,6
Baux index > 81-100, n=27	6,3±1,2	11,0±1,4	15,6±1,5	17,0±0,8
Baux index > 100, n=13	6,9±1,7	12,2±1,5	15,0±1,9	17,3±2,1

ADP was performed on average over an area of $9.8 \pm 0.2\%$ of total body surface area (Table 4). The average area of ADP did not significantly differ between the early and delayed surgical debridement groups. In all cases, efforts were made to maximize coverage of deep skin defects with autografts, resulting in significant differences in ADP area among subgroups with different severity of thermal injury. According to the extent of debridement, autodermoplasty was performed on different areas in patients with Baux index within 60-80 units and in those with Baux index over 100 units, covering areas of $7.6 \pm 0.5\%$ and $12.6 \pm 1.3\%$ of total body surface area, respectively.

Table 4.

Average area of ADP during debridement

Groups	ADP area* (body surface %)		
	ESD, n=22	DSD, n=47	Total
Baux index 60-80, n=29	6,7±0,9	7,9±0,7	7,6±0,5
Baux index > 81-100, n=27	13,2±1,6	11,7±0,9	12,8±0,8
Baux index > 100, n=13	14,3±2,6	12,4±1,1	12,6±1,3
Total, n=69	9,8±0,4	9,9±0,3	9,8±0,2

* - If staged ADP was performed, the area of the first stage was taken into account.

Staged ADP was used to close all deep defects in one stage for 53 (76.8%) elderly and aged patients, and in two stages for 16 (23.2%). In the group of patients who underwent ESD (n=22), a total of 31 ADP procedures were performed: one successful procedure for 16 patients, two-stage procedures for 3 patients, repeated procedures due to graft lysis for 4 patients, and 3 procedures in one case (two-stage ADP followed by repeat autograft due to graft lysis).

Among burn patients with DSD (n=47), a total of 51 ADP procedures were performed: one successful procedure for 34 patients, two-stage autograft for 4 patients, and repeat operations due to graft lysis after one-stage (n=3) and two-stage procedures (n=1).

The average time for skin recovery after trauma with surgical necrectomy was 30.6 ± 2.0 days on average, with 28.4 ± 1.7 days for ESD group and 32.2 ± 1.6 days for DSD group (a difference of 4 days on average, $p < 0.05$). These indicators also significantly differed between groups of patients with Baux index less than 80 and more than 100.

Longer skin recovery times in individuals with extensive and deep burns were due to both staged ADP and local complications, as well as epithelialization rates of IIIA-degree burns, which

healed within 21-28 days. Against the background of ESD with simultaneous autodermoplasty, the average skin recovery time was 19.6±1.9 days, allowing for a reduction in treatment duration by 3-8 days compared to average values in the DSD group.

Complications were noted in 9 (13.0%) out of 69 elderly patients, with pneumonia observed in all cases of complications. Other complications of burn disease occurred at a frequency of 1.4-4.3%. A nearly twofold increase in complication rates was observed in burned patients with more severe thermal trauma (Baux > 100), which was expected. However, no significant difference in complication rates was found between the ESD and DSD groups. It is noteworthy that none of the 8 patients with limited (less than 10% body surface) deep burns who underwent ESD with simultaneous autodermoplasty experienced burn disease complications.

Six (8.7%) out of 69 operated burn patients of elderly age experienced fatal outcomes after surgical necrectomy. Pneumonia was the immediate cause of death in 3 patients. In 1 patient, acute heart failure due to acute myocardial infarction was the immediate cause of death, and pulmonary embolism was the cause in 2 patients.

Thus, in elderly and aged burn patients, early surgical necrectomy, contrary to concerns of some specialists, did not significantly worsen mortality rates.

Graft lysis in elderly and aged burn patients occurred in approximately every fifth case – in 14 (20.3%) patients who underwent surgical necrectomy with subsequent ADP. In groups with different severity of thermal trauma, the frequency of graft lysis varied from 13.8% (Baux = 60-80) to 30.8% (Baux > 100). However, with an observation count of 69, the difference in indicators was not statistically significant (p>0.05) (Table 5). The fact that this complication occurs in every third patient with more severe thermal trauma (Baux > 100) is likely due to the severe condition of the patients and the use of a higher perforation ratio of flaps (1:4, 1:6).

Table 5.

Frequency of autodermotransplant graft lysis, n (%).

Groups	Lysis < 10%	Lysis 10-50%	Lysis > 50%	Total
Baux index 60-80, n=29	2 (6,9)	2 (6,9)	-	4 (13,8)
Baux index > 81-100, n=27	3 (11,1)	2 (7,4)	1 (3,7)	6 (22,2)
Baux index > 100, n=13	2 (15,4)	1 (7,7)	1 (7,7)	4 (30,8)
Total, n=69	7 (10,1)	5 (7,2)	2 (2,9)	14 (20,3)

The total and subtotal graft lysis occurred in only 2 cases (2.9% of all lysis cases). Partial (up to 50%) rejection of the transplanted autologous skin was much more frequent, observed in 12 patients (17.3% of all lysis cases).

During simultaneous autodermoplasty, where skin grafts were placed on the excised burn wound, the frequency of graft lysis was 11.8% (2 cases out of 17 ADP procedures). However, with delayed grafting onto granulating wounds, this rate doubled to 23.1% (12 out of 52 cases).

In elderly patients after performing ESD, out of 22 ADP cases, only 3 episodes of graft lysis were recorded (13.6%). Interestingly, this complication was slightly more frequent in patients with delayed ADP compared to those with simultaneous grafting (21.4% versus 12.5%). Following DSD, 10 cases of graft lysis were observed among 47 patients (21.3%). Notably, patients undergoing simultaneous ADP had significantly better outcomes, experiencing graft lysis more than twice as rarely as those with delayed skin grafting (11.1% versus 23.7%).

Comparison of graft lysis rates between ESD and DSD (18.2% and 21.3%, respectively) did not reveal a statistically significant difference.

Thus, when employing surgical debridement followed by autodermoplasty for treating deep burns in elderly patients, the average skin recovery period after injury was 30.6±2.0 days. The average frequency of autodermotransplant graft lysis was 20.3%. Notably, better outcomes were achieved with simultaneous autodermoplasty compared to delayed ADP (11.8% versus 23.1%). Complications were noted in 9 out of 69 patients (13.0%), all of whom developed pneumonia. The average postoperative mortality rate among burned patients with thermal injuries was 8.7%, with mortality

not exceeding 6.9% in patients with a Baux index of 60-80, but reaching 11.1% in patients with more severe trauma.

Conclusions.

1. The application of surgical debridement methods in elderly patient groups significantly reduces the recovery time of skin surface, frequency of burn disease complications, and mortality rates.
2. The rational application of early surgical treatment methods in elderly patients should be carried out following appropriate preoperative preparation and stabilization of their condition.
3. Simultaneous autodermoplasty with closure of all wounds in one stage is effective for limited deep burns.
4. Delayed autodermoplasty performed in 1-2 stages yields better outcomes for extensive burns in elderly patients.

REFERENCES| ЧОҚКИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. Alekseyev A.A., Bobrovnikov A.E. Analiz rezultatov vnedreniya v klinicheskuyu praktiku innovatsionnix texnologiy lecheniya postradavshix s ojogami // Kombustiologiya. Elektronniy nauchno-prakticheskiy jurnal. 2019. № 63-64. (in Russ.)
2. Alekseev AA, Bobrovnikov AE, Malyutina NB, Filimonov KA. Analiz i osobennosti raboty ozhogovykh statsionarov v Rossii v 2022 godu. Materialy vsrossiiskoi nauchno-prakticheskoi konferentsii «Ozhogi: diagnostika, lechenie, reabilitatsiya» - Kombustiologiya. 2021;69–70. Dostupno po: <http://combustiolog.ru/journal/2-chasttezisy-vsrossijskoj-nauchno-prakticheskoy-konferentsii-ozhogidiagnostika-lechenie-reabilitatsiya> (in Russ.)
3. Atyasova M.L. Osobennosti lecheniya glubokix ojogov u pojilix //Aktualniye voprosi xirurgii, travmatologii i intensivnoy terapii: materialy region, nauch.- prakt. konf.- Saransk, 2011.- C. 149-151. (in Russ.)
4. Malaxov S. F. Osnovniye napravleniya ispolzovaniya sovremennix ranevix pokritiy v lechenii obshirnix glubokix ojogov //Voprosi nauki i obrazovaniya. – 2017. – №. 7 (8). – C. 83-85. (in Russ.)
5. Fayazov A. D., Ajiniyazov R. S. Osobennosti techeniya ojogovoy bolezni u lits pojilogo i starcheskogo vozrasta //Skoraya meditsinskaya pomosh. – 2020. – T. 21. – №. 3. – C. 54-57. (in Russ.)
6. Xadjibayev A. M., Fayazov A. D., Sultanov B. K. Effektivnost ranney nekrektomii u bolnix pojilogo i starcheskogo vozrasta //Skoraya meditsinskaya pomosh. – 2006. – T. 7. – №. 3. – C. 162-163. (in Russ.)
7. Thompson A., Gida S., Nassif Y., Hope C., Brooks A. The impact of frailty on trauma outcomes using the Clinical Frailty Scale // Eur J Trauma Emerg Surg. (2021), P. 1-6
8. Farinas A.F., Bamba R., Pollins A.C., Cardwell N.L., Nanney L.B., Thayer W.P. Burn wounds in the young versus the aged patient display differential immunological responses // Burns., 44 (6) (2018), P. 1475-1481
9. Tian J., Cheng L.H, Cui X, Lei X.X, Tang J.B, Cheng B. Application of standardized platelet-rich plasma in elderly patients with complex wounds. Wound Repair Regen. 2019;27:3: 268–276
10. Maxwell D., Rhee P., Drake M., Hodge J., Ingram W., Williams R. Development of the Burn Frailty Index: A prognostication index for elderly patients sustaining burn injuries// Am J Surg., 218 (2019), pp. 87-94,
11. Alimjanovich , R. Z., Maxammatkulovich , R. N., & Khikmatovich , K. K. (2022). Age Features of the Prevalence of Prostate Cancer in Uzbekistan. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(5), 154-157. Retrieved from
12. Rizaev Jasur , Rakhimov Nodir , Kodyrov Khamidullo , Shakhanova Shakhnoza . Study

- of prostate cancer death by regions of the republic of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice*. 2022, vol . 7, issue 5, pp.202-210
13. Nodir RM, Shaxnoza SS, Farhod R. Development of new approaches in the treatment of metastatic renal cell carcinoma // *Journal of research in health science*. – 2020. – Т. 5. – no. 4. – pp. 82-95.
 14. ShSh Shakhanova , NM Rakhimov. Multimodal approach to the treatment of multiple osteogenic metastases of kidney and prostate cancer . *Clinical and Experimental Oncology* 2020, No. 4 Page 50-56.
 15. Romanowski K. , Curtis E. , Barsun A., Palmieri T., Greenhalgh D. , Sen S. The frailty tipping point: determining which patients are targets for intervention in a burn population// *Burns*., 45 (2019), pp. 1051-1056
 16. S. Church, E. Rogers, K. Rockwood, O. Theou. A scoping review of the Clinical Frailty Scale// *BMC Geriatrics*., 20 (2020), p. 393

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

10 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 1

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000